

Supplementary material for article:

Land use modelling needs to better account for multiple cropping to inform pathways for sustainable agriculture

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Supplementary Note 1. Intercropping in Africa

We used data from the Living Standards Measurement Study – Integrated Surveys on Agriculture (LSMS-ISA) in seven African countries (Supplementary Table S1) to estimate the prevalence of intercropping on a household and plot level. Each survey includes questions on the use of intercropping on a plot the household owns/manages (“Have you practiced intercropping on this plot in the last twelve months”) and the plot area. We gave preference to plot area measured with a handheld GPS device and only used self-reported area where no other information was available. There are strong regional differences in terms of the occurrence of intercropping practices (Supplementary Figure S1). About half or more of the cultivated crop area is under intercropping in Malawi, Niger, Tanzania, and Uganda.

Supplementary Figure S1. Percentage cultivated crop area under intercropping and single cropping in seven African countries.

Supplementary Table S1. National surveys used for the analysis of intercropping prevalence.

Country	Survey Name	Producer(s)	DOI
Burkina Faso	Enquête Multisectorielle Continue 2014	Institut National de la Statistique et de la Démographie	https://doi.org/10.48529/e39g-m952
Ethiopia	Socioeconomic Survey 2018-2019	Central Statistics Agency of Ethiopia	https://doi.org/10.48529/k739-c548
Malawi	Fifth Integrated Household Survey 2019-2020	National Statistical Office (NSO)	https://doi.org/10.48529/yqn3-zv74
Mali	Enquête Agricole de Conjoncture Intégrée aux Conditions de Vie des Ménages 2017	Cellule de Planification et de Statistiques, Institut National de la Statistique, Direction Nationale de l'Agriculture	https://doi.org/10.48529/0v50-h966
Niger	Enquête Harmonisée sur le Conditions de Vie des Ménages 2018-2019	Institut National de la Statistique (INS)	https://doi.org/10.48529/ggam-ax39
Tanzania	National Panel Survey 2019-2020 - Extended Panel with Sex Disaggregated Data	World Bank	https://doi.org/10.48529/0y7d-1v78
Uganda	National Panel Survey 2019-2020	Uganda Bureau of Statistics	https://doi.org/10.48529/nqzx-f196

Supplementary Note 2. Other spatially explicit multiple cropping area estimates

Where the type of multiple cropping system cannot be identified directly, other methods include to (i) estimate potentially suitable areas for multiple cropping based on soil and/or climate ¹⁻⁵ and (ii) calculate average cropping frequency and cropping intensity. The latter are key crop cultivation indicators and important measures of multiple cropping practices. They can be defined as the number of crop planting and harvesting cycles within a full year or as the ratio of harvested to physical area available ².

On national to global scales, a range of studies have estimated cropping intensity using the growing season peak detection-based algorithm and high temporal frequency vegetation index time series, e.g., moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer (MODIS). For example, Estel et al. ⁶ used MODIS NDVI time series to map cropping intensity in Europe from 2000 to 2012 at a spatial resolution of about 200 meters. Qiu et al. and Yan et al. ^{7,8} mapped cropping intensity in China during 2000–2015 and 2015–2021 using the MODIS Surface Reflectance Product (MOD09A1) time series imagery with a 500 m spatial resolution and an 8-day interval. Cropping intensity from 2009 to 2012 throughout Asia was mapped using the time series segmentation process used to generate the MODIS Land Cover Dynamics product ⁹. On the global scale, Wu et al. ⁵ mapped cropping intensity for the year 2010 based on the NASA third-generation Global Inventory Monitoring and Modeling System with a spatial resolution of 8 km and 15-day interval. The spatial resolution of such map was later improved to 5.6 km ¹⁰ and 500 m ¹¹ as part of the Collection 6 MODIS Land Cover Dynamics dataset. Finally, Liu et al. ¹² demonstrated methods for mapping cropping intensity in eight world regions on a 30 m resolution that were later used to produce a global, spatially continuous cropping intensity map for 2016–2018 ¹³. This approach can be extended from single-year to multi-year time series of crop cycles to indicate the existence of three crop cycles in two years or five crop cycles in 3 years ¹⁴.

Two major limitations of cropping intensity measures based on MODIS are that they cannot represent the actual crop combinations or reflect the actual crop growth duration, which is important to understand multiple cropping practices ^{15,16}. To address the first problem, it is sometimes possible to match the planting period detectable from satellite images to a specific crop or crop season as often possible for rice ¹⁷. The second problem can lead to an overestimation of potential cropping intensity compared to current cropping intensity when it is assumed that an additional harvest is possible in mono-cropping systems where the single crop already grows over the entire growing season ^{4,15}. Further challenges exist

with respect to missing data due to lack of cloud-free observations and sub-pixel variation in cropping practices ⁹, both especially relevant in low latitudes and for countries with small field sizes. To further improve cropping intensity maps in China, Xiang et al. ¹⁸ used satellite images with higher spatial and temporal resolution for South China in 2015 to better distinguish the nuances found in fragmented landscapes and induced by crop rotation.

Supplementary Table S2. Overview of selected crop model skills reported in the scientific literature. Rather than providing a systematic review, we here focus on most recent studies reflecting model developments. The column “No. of models” provides counts of all models included in the studies and in brackets the number of models considered to have at least basic skills according to the respective study authors. Some studies provide both, a review and a new model development, e.g. Githui et al. ¹⁹.

Study scope	Type of study	Key findings regarding modelling skills	Spatial scale and region	No. of models	Models included	Refs
Crop rotations	Model ensemble	- slightly better skill of simulations if rotations are considered - common cereals typically better represented than intermediate crops (e.g., oilseeds, grasses)	Multi-site (Europe)	14 (10)	APSIM, CROPSYST, Daisy, DSSAT, FASSET, HERMES, LPJmL, MONICA, SIMPLACE, SPACSYS, STICS, SWIM, Theseus, WOFOST	²⁰
Crop rotations	Model ensemble	- similar model skill with dynamic rotations compared to single crops - good skill for productivity, poorer skill for soil-based GHG emissions	Multi-site (Americas, Asia, Europe, Oceania)	14 (14)	Agro-C, APSIM, CERES-EGC, DayCent, DailyDayCent, DNDC, DSSAT, EPIC, FASSET, INFOCROP, Landscape-DNDC, LPJmL, SALUS, STICS	²¹
Cover crops	Individual models	- reasonable performance of APSIM for maize-soy-winter rye in US mid-west regarding productivity, SOC, and temporal interactions - reasonable simulation of N leaching reductions with cover crops in DSSAT but less skill in soil ON at lysimeter site in Spain - thorough calibration of STICS allows for robust prediction of cover crop emergence in France - implementation of cover crops in global gridded crop model LPJmL indicates results mostly in the range of meta-analyses for various outputs (crop yield, SOC sequestration, N leaching among others)	Site (ESP, FRA), regional (USA), global	4 (4)	APSIM, DSSAT, LPJmL, STICS	²²⁻²⁵
Sequential cropping	Individual models	- ORYZA2000 capable of simulating multiple rice seasons at experimental site - calibrated APSIM capable of evaluation of crop water use on experimental site for various types of cropping systems and crop combinations - EPIC provides distinct impacts on crop growth in double-cropping seasons, crop calendar optimization needs to consider fallow requirements	Site (CHN, SEN), regional (IND)	3 (3)	APSIM, ORYZA, EPIC	²⁶⁻²⁸

Study scope	Type of study	Key findings regarding modelling skills	Spatial scale and region	No. of models	Models included	Refs
Intercropping	Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1D approach used in all cropping system models reviewed - basic representation of competition - below-ground heterogeneity and spatial arrangement of roots (2D) only in specialized agroforestry model WaNuLCAS - cropping system models have been developed with reductions perspective which contrasts the complexity in intercropping 	-	7 (5)	APSIM, AquaCrop, EPIC (ALMANAC), STICS, CERES, SWB, WaNuLCAS	²⁹
Intercropping	Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interactions mostly limited to 1D resource sharing - specialized models have much higher skills but were only calibrated for specific crops and may lack other crop management processes - performance of cropping systems models for simulating intercropping in typically poor - impacts of crop-soil management (e.g., tillage, mulching) remains understudied 	-	7 (3)	APSIM, DSSAT, FASSET, STICS, SWAP 2x1D, WaNuLCAS, FSP	¹⁹
Intercropping	Individual models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - poor performance of APSIM in a test for Australia - improved version of STICS can generically reflect plant-plant interactions in strip intercropping with reasonable performance and representation of key processes incl. plasticity of intercrops 	Multi-site (AUS, FRA)	2 (2)	APSIM, STICS	^{19,30}
Agroforestry	Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - focus on modelling of ecosystem services in agroforestry at large - out of cropping systems models, moderately high skill is attributed to APSIM - regulation of water is best represented - specialized agroforestry models have typically high crop specificity 	-	13 (2)	APSIM, COMP8, DynACof, EPIC, ESAT-A, Hi-sAFe, HyPAR, ICBM/N, SBELTS, SCUAF, WaNuLCAS, WIMISIA, Yield-sAFe	³¹
Mechanistic models for crop diversification (all of the above)	Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - most cropping systems models (here agroecosystem models) allow for spatial or temporal heterogeneity - in-field heterogeneity of input data (i.e., soil) is typically not considered - marginal crops are highly underrepresented compared to major cereals - field arrangements can hardly be reproduced - biological interactions are lacking 	-	24+ (17)	APSIM, CropSyst, Daisy, DND, DNDC, DNDC95, LandscapeDNDC, EPIC, FASSET, STICS, Agro-C, AGROTOOL, AquaCrop, DAYCENT, DSSAT, HERMES, Hi-sAFe, LPJmL, MONICA, SALUS, SIMPLACE, SPACSYS, SWAT+EPIC, SWAT-C, SWIM, THESEUS, WaNuLCAS, WOFOST	³²

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